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Chemical Investigation of *Ochna squarrosa*

Linn

K. K. PURUSHOTHAMAN*, A. SARADA
and

M. BALAKRISHNAN

Captain Srinivasa Murthi Drug Research Institute for Ayurveda,
Madras-29

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OCHNA SQUARROSA Linn. (Ochnaceae) is a medicinally important plant used in Indian system of medicine for various diseases¹. The earlier workers reported the presence of β -sitosterol from the plant². In this communication we report three more known compounds-*n*-octacosanol, campesterol and β -sitosterol glycoside.

Experimental

Air dried powdered whole plant (2 kg) was successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), chloroform and methanol. The petrol extract was concentrated and column chromatographed over silica gel. On elution with hexane-benzene 1:1 mixture resulted in a colourless material which on crystallisation using hexane yielded a compound, m.p. 84°. This compound was identified as octacosanol by comparison with an authentic sample.

The chloroform extract was chromatographed over silica gel and on elution with benzene afforded white solid, m.p. 156° which on acetylation with acetic anhydride-pyridine furnished the corresponding acetate, m.p. 138° identical with an authentic specimen of campesterol acetate.

Further elution of the column with chloroform afforded a glycoside, m.p. 284° which on hydrolysis with methanolic hydrochloric acid gave an aglycone m.p. 136-37°, identical with an authentic sample of β -sitosterol. The sugar moiety after usual work up was identified as glucose, by paper chromatography. Finally the glycoside itself was compared with an authentic sample (m.p. and m.m.p.) and was found to be identical.

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